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In [16]: #This code is produced to support Chapter 8 of the Phd thesis by Hana Sediva. Written in December 2023.
#It demonstrates the use of various feature selection models used for all ten target behaviours.
#Specifically, it uses univariate feature selection, feature ranking, correlation matrix, and recursive feature elimination
#with cross validation (RFECV)
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```
In [124... #Univariate Selection for Steps feature selection
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-1] #target column i.e garmin steps
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for Steps','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('steps_univariate.xlsx', index=False)
```

	Predictors for Steps	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	327847.472590
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	3146.387804
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	2424.896402
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1648.619666
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	940.100000
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	119.060000
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	115.000000
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	113.968706
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	111.000000
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	106.000000

```
In [100... #Feature Importance for Steps
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import random
random.seed(10)
```

```
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -1] #target column Garmin steps
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(10).plot(kind='barh')
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for steps', loc='center', color='black', size=14)
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02399437 0.04403649 0.02864486 0.02451825 0.08121314 0.06906775
 0.08685487 0.02093649 0.09786574 0.01703602 0.09790023 0.01440148
 0.02603617 0.03116663 0.0268945 0.03034642 0.04031107 0.04012477
 0.02135894 0.07787326 0.03394875 0.0654698 ]
```

Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model
with predictors for steps


```
In [63]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -1] #target column is steps count
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for Steps', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
```

```
#plot heat map  
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for Steps


```
In [17]: # compare machine learning models for regression for steps count
```

```
from numpy import mean
from numpy import std
from sklearn.datasets import make_regression
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsRegressor
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
from sklearn.svm import SVR
from matplotlib import pyplot
import pandas as pd

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
# get the dataset
def get_dataset():
    X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
    y = data.iloc[:, -1] #target column Garmin steps
    return X, y

# get a list of models to evaluate
def get_models():
```

```

models = dict()
models['knn'] = KNeighborsRegressor()
models['cart'] = DecisionTreeRegressor()
models['svm'] = SVR()
models['rfr'] = RandomForestRegressor()
models['gbr'] = GradientBoostingRegressor()
models['lm'] = LinearRegression()
return models

# evaluate a given model using cross-validation
def evaluate_model(model, X, y):
    cv = RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1)
    scores = cross_val_score(model, X, y, scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error', cv=cv, n_jobs=-1, error_score='raise')
    return scores

# define dataset
X, y = get_dataset()
# get the models to evaluate
models = get_models()
# evaluate the models and store results
results, names = list(), list()
for name, model in models.items():
    scores = evaluate_model(model, X, y)
    results.append(scores)
    names.append(name)
    print('>%s %.3f (%.3f)' % (name, mean(scores), std(scores)))
# plot model performance for comparison
pyplot.boxplot(results, labels=names, showmeans=True)
pyplot.title('Comparison of ML models for predicting steps count')
pyplot.ylabel('Performance accuracy using neg RMSE value')
pyplot.xlabel('ML models')
pyplot.show()

```

```

>knn -4438.403 (938.889)
>cart -4985.835 (1129.880)
>svm -4796.831 (1177.931)
>rfr -3777.701 (862.884)
>gbr -3994.775 (678.400)
>lm -3671.578 (690.924)

```



```
In [21]: #using RFE feature selection for steps
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(123)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
```

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y = data.iloc[:, -1]    #target column Garmin steps

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')
rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:", rfecv.get_feature_names_out())

plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for steps count versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()

rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)

```

Optimum number of features: 6

Selected feature names: ['ema_veg_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary' 'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA']

Total features selected for steps count versus RMSE

Out[21]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	2
ema_fruit_portions_goal	3
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	4
ema_daily_total_education_shown	5
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	6
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	7
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	8
ema_human_coach_interaction	9
ema_daily_total_education_read	10
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	11
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	12
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	13
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	14
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	15
ema_steps_goal_binary	16
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	17

```
In [13]: #Univariate Selection for total sleep feature selection  
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -3] #target column i.e garmin total sleep minutes
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for Total Sleep minutes','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('total_sleep_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for Total Sleep minutes	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	264546.061818
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	2609.291233
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	2167.105047
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1315.442199
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	878.966667
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	103.380000
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	95.859375
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	92.082504
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	89.902778
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	81.500000

In [108..

```

#Feature Importance for total sleep
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -3] #target column total sleep
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(23).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for total Sleep minutes', loc='center', color='black')
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02375744 0.05065847 0.02460516 0.02054155 0.07859367 0.0695843
 0.09526891 0.02014664 0.09394893 0.01369743 0.09678383 0.01313265
 0.03121474 0.03192698 0.02838967 0.03480888 0.03115296 0.04085699
 0.02303949 0.07840518 0.04100928 0.05847686]
```



```
In [66]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -3] #target column total sleep
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for total sleep minutes', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for total sleep minutes


```
In [35]: #using RFE feature selection for total sleep
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(200)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-3] #target column total sleep

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for total sleep minutes versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()
```

```
rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 7

Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_education_shown' 'ema_veg_portions_goal'
'ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA']

Out[35]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	2
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	3
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	4
ema_human_coach_interaction	5
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	6
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	7
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	8
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	9
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	10
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	11
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	12
ema_daily_total_education_read	13
ema_steps_goal_binary	14
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	15
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	16

```
In [126... #Univariate Selection for Deep Sleep feature selection  
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-2] #target column garmin deep sleep minutes
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for Deep Sleep minutes','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('deep_sleep_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for Deep Sleep minutes	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	272357.145347
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	2314.908420
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1854.849855
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1313.534809
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	818.650000
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	94.710937
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	94.560000
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	91.786273
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	89.567073
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	86.159722

In [104...

```

#Feature Importance for Deep Sleep
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-2] #target column Deep Sleep
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(23).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for Deep Sleep minutes', loc='center', color='black')
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.01831463 0.04798186 0.02560078 0.0218927 0.07849007 0.06733393
0.09293764 0.02431317 0.09067288 0.01480905 0.09771642 0.01216701
0.03190888 0.03504278 0.0255346 0.02916542 0.04013048 0.03992111
0.02314576 0.07924961 0.03685837 0.06681286]
```



```
In [69]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-2] #target column Deep Sleep minutes
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for Deep Sleep minutes', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for Deep Sleep minutes


```
In [36]: #using RFE feature selection for deep sleep
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(300)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-2] #target column deep sleep

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```

plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for deep sleep minutes versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()

```

```

rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)

```

Optimum number of features: 4

Selected feature names: ['ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA']

Out[36]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	2
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	3
ema_daily_total_education_shown	4
ema_daily_total_education_read	5
ema_fruit_portions_goal	6
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	7
ema_human_coach_interaction	8
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	9
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	10
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	11
ema_steps_goal_binary	12
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	13
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	14
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	15
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	16
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	17
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	18
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	19

```
In [146... #Univariate Selection for Fruit feature selection
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-9] #target column fruit portions
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for portions of Fruit','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('fruit_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for portions of Fruit	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	24980.188274
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	538.533071
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	403.964679
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	349.689776
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	168.881773
5	ema_fruit_portions_goal	15.228267
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	11.126966
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	10.657237
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	10.030419
17	ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	10.008471

In [123...

```

#Feature Importance for Fruit
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-9] #target column fruit
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(22).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for portions of Fruit consumption', loc='center',
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02488834 0.04665649 0.03060134 0.0236638 0.07226349 0.07969083
0.08231502 0.02539474 0.0828324 0.01594654 0.08948465 0.02001967
0.0296391 0.04229642 0.02421709 0.03003039 0.03675259 0.03626602
0.02513034 0.08054928 0.03773453 0.06362691]
```



```
In [72]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -9] #target column Fruit portions
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of Fruit consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of Fruit consumption


```
In [37]: #using RFE feature selection for fruit portions
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(400)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -9] #target column fruit portions

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:", rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for fruit portions versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()
```

```
rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 3

Selected feature names: ['ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA']

Out[37]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	2
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	3
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	4
ema_veg_portions_goal	5
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	6
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	7
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	8
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	9
ema_daily_total_education_read	10
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	11
ema_daily_total_education_shown	12
ema_human_coach_interaction	13
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	14
ema_steps_goal_binary	15
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	16
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	17
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	18
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	19
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	20

```
In [127... #Univariate Selection for Veg feature selection
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-8] #target column veg portions
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for portions of Vegetables','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('veg_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for portions of Vegetables	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	23788.472858
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	676.082716
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	588.140717
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	511.806061
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	72.065614
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	38.811038
17	ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	20.816964
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	20.542227
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	11.765474
13	ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	11.229684

In [128..

```

#Feature Importance for veg
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-8] #target column veg
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(23).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for portions of Veg consumption', loc='center', co
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02422938 0.04862285 0.02363426 0.02468081 0.08303881 0.06547153
 0.08823264 0.02164595 0.08946263 0.01897889 0.09064096 0.01532442
 0.03430795 0.03542613 0.02643815 0.03528569 0.03614038 0.03812273
 0.02284273 0.07922695 0.04092698 0.0573192 ]
```



```
In [75]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for portions of vegetables
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-8] #target column veg portions
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of Veg consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of Veg consumption


```
In [39]: #using RFE feature selection for veg portions
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(500)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-8] #target column veg portions

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for vegetables portions versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()

rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 20

Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_surveys_answered' 'ema_daily_total_education_shown'
'ema_daily_total_education_read'
'ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary' 'ema_veg_portions_goal'
'ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary' 'ema_had_alcohol_last_night'
'ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary'
'ema_group_exercise_participation_binary'
'ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_steps_goal_binary'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA' 'ema_human_coach_interaction'
'ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale']

Total features selected for vegetables portions versus RMSE

Out[39]:

	Rank
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_binary	1
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	1
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	1
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_human_coach_interaction	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	2
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	3

In [129...]

```
#Univariate Selection for Water feature selection  
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -10] #target column water glasses
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for glasses of water consumption','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('water_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for glasses of water consumption	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	31617.904291
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	217.393040
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	174.036670
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	148.409559
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	98.069156
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	37.967660
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	14.843382
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	12.214939
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	8.356924
20	ema_human_coach_interaction	7.919118

In [131...

```

#Feature Importance for water
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -10] #target column water glasses
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(23).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for glasses of water intake', loc='center', color=
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02349191 0.04645777 0.03515223 0.02565447 0.09924602 0.07511963
0.08203801 0.02326051 0.08491291 0.01877834 0.08640698 0.00979925
0.03200938 0.03308767 0.02318358 0.03181851 0.03909678 0.03466625
0.0243871 0.07288147 0.03597842 0.0625728 ]
```



```
In [78]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for glasses of water
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -10] #target column water glasses
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for glasses of water intake', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for glasses of water intake


```
In [40]: #using RFE feature selection for water glasses
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(600)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-10] #target column water glasses

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```

plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for number of glasses of water versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()

rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)

```

Optimum number of features: 14

Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_surveys_answered' 'ema_daily_total_education_shown'
'ema_daily_total_education_read' 'ema_veg_portions_goal'
'ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_had_alcohol_last_night' 'ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA' 'ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale']

Out[40]:

	Rank
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	1
ema_human_coach_interaction	2
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	3
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	4
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	5
ema_steps_goal_binary	6
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	7
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	8
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	9

In [132...]

```
#Univariate Selection for Caffeine feature selection  
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -7] #target column caffeine cups
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for cups of Coffee intake','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('caffeine_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for cups of Coffee intake	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	18090.109980
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	300.480150
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	273.216216
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	88.944773
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	22.473818
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	11.869682
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	10.335758
1	ema_daily_total_education_shown	6.378251
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	5.128239
16	ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	4.570158

In [133..

```

#Feature Importance for caffeine
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -7] #target column caffeine cups
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(23).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for cups of coffee consumption', loc='center', col
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.03360324 0.12135406 0.02248226 0.02376501 0.08777253 0.06832468
0.08607956 0.01837266 0.07092232 0.02244507 0.0731783 0.01102311
0.03108247 0.03295119 0.0240834 0.03500934 0.02922412 0.03073906
0.02104344 0.07765159 0.03005514 0.04883746]
```



```
In [81]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for cups of coffee
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -7] #target column caffeine cups
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for cups of coffee consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for cups of coffee consumption


```
In [41]: #using RFE feature selection for coffee cups
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(700)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -7] #target column coffee cups

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:", rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for cups of coffee versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()
```

```
rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 12

Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_surveys_answered' 'ema_daily_total_education_shown'
'ema_daily_total_education_read' 'ema_veg_portions_goal'
'ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_had_alcohol_last_night' 'ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA']

Out[41]:

	Rank
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	2
ema_human_coach_interaction	3
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	4
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	5
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	6
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	7
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	8
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	9
ema_steps_goal_binary	10
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	11

```
In [137... #Univariate Selection for alcohol feature selection
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -6] #target column alcohol
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for units of alcoholic beverages consumption','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('alcohol_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for units of alcoholic beverages consumption	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	40485.696573
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	135.195504
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	111.000000
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	101.818845
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	94.580405
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	30.716159
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	13.104624
3	ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	13.067703
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	12.404757
20	ema_human_coach_interaction	10.710250

In [142...

```

#Feature Importance for alcohol
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -6] #target column alcohol
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(22).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for units of alcoholic beverages consumption', loc
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.01373095 0.02586146 0.0221662 0.0266565 0.03603955 0.03497836
0.05005422 0.01266565 0.05492256 0.00422981 0.04415016 0.00157255
0.40084689 0.02695224 0.02677064 0.02621476 0.01524994 0.01695443
0.01658982 0.05832259 0.03811088 0.04695981]
```



```
In [84]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for units of alcohol
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-6] #target column units of alcohol
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for units of alcoholic beverages consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```



```
In [42]: #using RFE feature selection for units of alcohol
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(800)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-6] #target column units of alcohol

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for units of alcohol versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()
```

```
rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 15

```
Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_education_shown' 'ema_daily_total_education_read'
'ema_veg_portions_goal' 'ema_fruit_portions_goal'
'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_had_alcohol_last_night' 'ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary'
'ema_group_exercise_participation_binary' 'ema_steps_goal_binary'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA' 'ema_human_coach_interaction'
'ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale']
```

Total features selected for units of alcohol versus RMSE

Out[42]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_binary	1
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	1
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	1
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	1
ema_human_coach_interaction	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	2
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	3
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	4
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	5
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	6
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	7
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	8

```
In [140... #Univariate Selection for snacks feature selection
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-5] #target column snacks
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for portions of snacks consumption','Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10,'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('snacks_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for portions of snacks consumption	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	25153.578331
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	289.580549
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	116.610552
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	83.490092
15	ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	15.804265
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	10.643060
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	8.596621
20	ema_human_coach_interaction	6.847514
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	5.584556
4	ema_veg_portions_goal	5.524118

In [143...

```

#Feature Importance for snacks
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-5] #target column snacks
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(22).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for portions of snacks consumption', loc='center',
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.02332289 0.04670947 0.03562508 0.03296244 0.07541456 0.07655741
0.09099345 0.01951725 0.08088367 0.01809192 0.07305303 0.0137455
0.04205881 0.0361773 0.0325865 0.03991952 0.03656593 0.04619926
0.01673433 0.0746867 0.04008089 0.0481141 ]
```



```
In [87]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for number of snacks
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -5] #target column snacks
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of snacks consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for portions of snacks consumption


```
In [44]: #using RFE feature selection for portions of snacks
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(900)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-5] #target column snacks

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for number of snacks versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()

rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 19

Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_surveys_answered' 'ema_daily_total_education_shown'
'ema_daily_total_education_read'
'ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary' 'ema_veg_portions_goal'
'ema_fruit_portions_goal' 'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary' 'ema_had_alcohol_last_night'
'ema_group_exercise_participation_binary'
'ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_steps_goal_binary'
'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA' 'ema_human_coach_interaction'
'ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale']

Total features selected for number of snacks versus RMSE

Out[44]:

	Rank
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_binary	1
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	1
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_human_coach_interaction	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_veg_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	1
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	2
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	3
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	4

```
In [144... #Univariate Selection for number of meals feature selection  
import pandas as pd
```

```

import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -4] #target column meals
#apply SelectKBest class to extract top 10 best features
bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=chi2, k=10)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,y)
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
dfcolumns = pd.DataFrame(X.columns)
#concat two dataframes for better visualization
featureScores = pd.concat([dfcolumns,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Predictors for number of meals consumption', 'Score'] #naming the dataframe columns
print(featureScores.nlargest(10, 'Score')) #print 10 best features

featureScores.to_excel('meals_univariate.xlsx', index=False)

```

	Predictors for number of meals consumption	Score
19	ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1631.654956
6	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	629.492951
8	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	556.106835
10	ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	251.009599
2	ema_daily_total_education_read	8.179459
14	ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	7.871622
12	ema_had_alcohol_last_night	7.343243
7	ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	7.192821
9	ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	4.887807
13	ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	4.774775

In [145...

```

#Feature Importance for meals
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -4] #target column meals
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = ExtraTreesClassifier()
model.fit(X,y)
print(model.feature_importances_) #use inbuilt class feature_importances of tree based classifiers
#plot graph of feature importances for better visualization
feat_importances = pd.Series(model.feature_importances_, index=X.columns)
feat_importances.nlargest(22).plot(kind='barh')

```

```
plt.title('Feature Importance (Tree Based Classifier) model \n with predictors for number of meals consumption', loc='center', co
plt.gca().invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel("Rating")
plt.ylabel("Predictors")
plt.show()
```

```
[0.00873239 0.012924 0.01053192 0.00682237 0.02218711 0.02186217
0.07188087 0.23141277 0.07563599 0.20436446 0.07249523 0.09724365
0.01771969 0.01814638 0.017203 0.01228527 0.0098336 0.02023591
0.00873944 0.02065946 0.01612792 0.02295641]
```



```
In [90]: #Correlation Matrix with Heatmap for number of meals
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
```

```
import seaborn as sns
data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:, -4] #target column number of meals
#get correlations of each features in dataset
corrmat = data.corr()
top_corr_features = corrmat.index
plt.figure(figsize=(20,20))
plt.title('Correlation matrix with predictors for number of meals consumption', loc='center', color='black', size=18)
#plot heat map
g=sns.heatmap(data[top_corr_features].corr(),annot=True,cmap="RdYlGn")
```

Correlation matrix with predictors for number of meals consumption


```
In [45]: #using RFE feature selection for meals
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from sklearn.feature_selection import RFECV
from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedKFold
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingRegressor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import random

random.seed(1000)

data = pd.read_csv("C:/R_code/study4/dfPredictors.csv")
X = data.iloc[:,0:22] #independent columns
y = data.iloc[:,-4] #target column meals

rfecv = RFECV(estimator=GradientBoostingRegressor(),
              step=1,
              cv=RepeatedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1),
              scoring='neg_root_mean_squared_error')

rfecv.fit(X, y)
print("Optimum number of features: %d" % rfecv.n_features_)
print("Selected feature names:",rfecv.get_feature_names_out())
```

```
plt.figure( figsize=(16, 6))
plt.title('Total features selected for number of meals versus RMSE')
plt.xlabel('Total features selected')
plt.ylabel('Model accuracy using neg RMSE')
plt.plot(range(1, len(rfecv.grid_scores_) + 1), rfecv.grid_scores_)
plt.show()
```

```
rfecv_df = pd.DataFrame(rfecv.ranking_, index=X.columns, columns=['Rank']).sort_values(by='Rank', ascending=True)
rfecv_df.head(22)
```

Optimum number of features: 16

```
Selected feature names: ['ema_daily_total_education_shown' 'ema_daily_total_education_read'
'ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary' 'ema_fruit_portions_goal'
'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA'
'ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary'
'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary'
'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA' 'ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary'
'ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary' 'ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary'
'ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary' 'ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA'
'ema_human_coach_interaction' 'ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale']
```


Out[45]:

	Rank
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_steps_goal_number_no_NA	1
ema_evening_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_morning_exercise_plan_binary	1
ema_achieved_planned_exercise_binary	1
ema_dinner_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_human_coach_interaction	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_sleep_quality_transformed_scale	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_binary	1
ema_breakfast_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_fruit_portions_goal	1
ema_daily_education_library_accessed_binary	1
ema_daily_total_education_read	1
ema_daily_total_education_shown	1
ema_lunch_colourful_rating_no_NA	1
ema_afternoon_exercise_plan_binary	2
ema_group_exercise_participation_binary	3
ema_veg_portions_goal	4
ema_daily_total_surveys_answered	5
ema_steps_goal_binary	6
ema_had_alcohol_last_night	7